

Table 1. Catalogue of Exoplanet Atmospheric Retrieval Codes

Code / Authors	Spectrum Type	Parameter Exploration	Code Link	References
Sampling Based				
Madhusudhan & Seager	Transmission Emission	Grid, MCMC	—	Madhusudhan & Seager (2009)
NEMESIS	Emission			Lee et al. (2012)
	Transmission Reflection	OE, NS	Link	Barstow et al. (2013) Barstow et al. (2014)
SCARLET	Transmission Emission	MCMC, NS	—	Benneke & Seager (2012)
	Reflection			Benneke et al. (2019) Wong et al. (2020)
MassSpec	Transmission	MCMC	—	de Wit & Seager (2013)
CHIMERA	Emission			Line et al. (2013)
	Transmission Reflection	OE, MCMC, NS, SC-Grid	Link	Swain et al. (2014) Piskorz et al. (2018)
TauREx	Transmission Emission	MCMC, NS	Link	Waldmann et al. (2015b)
				Waldmann et al. (2015a)
Lupu et al.	Reflection	MCMC, NS	—	Lupu et al. (2016)
HELIOS-R	Emission	NS	Link	Lavie et al. (2017)
APOLLO	Transmission Emission	MCMC	Link	Howe et al. (2017)
				Howe et al. (2022)
POSEIDON	Transmission Emission	NS	Link	MacDonald & Madhusudhan (2017)
				Coulombe et al. (2023)
ATMO	Transmission Emission	MCMC, NS, SC-Grid	—	Wakeford et al. (2017)
				Evans et al. (2017)
Brewster	Emission	MCMC, NS	Link	Burningham et al. (2017)
Pyrat Bay	Transmission Emission	MCMC	Link	Kilpatrick et al. (2018)
				Cubillos & Bleic (2021)
HyDRA	Emission	NS	—	Gandhi & Madhusudhan (2018)
	Reflection			
PSG	Emission	OE, NS	Link	Villanueva et al. (2018)
	Transmission			
AURA	Transmission	NS	—	Pinhas et al. (2018)
exoretrievals	Transmission	NS	—	Espinoza et al. (2019)
Brogi & Line	Emission	NS	Link	Brogi & Line (2019)
PLATON	Transmission Emission	NS	Link	Zhang et al. (2019)
				Zhang et al. (2020)
petitRADTRANS	Transmission	MCMC, NS	Link	Mollière et al. (2019)
	Emission			Mollière et al. (2019)
	Reflection			Alei et al. (2022)
Helios-r2	Emission	NS	—	Kitzmann et al. (2020)

Table 1 *continued*

Table 1 (*continued*)

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MERC	Transmission	NS	—	Seidel et al. (2020)
species	Emission	MCMC, NS, SC-Grid	Link	Stolker et al. (2020)
Gibson et al.	Transmission	MCMC	—	Gibson et al. (2020)
ExoReL ^R	Reflection	NS	—	Damiano & Hu (2020)
Alfnor	Transmission	NS	—	Changeat et al. (2020)
PETRA	Emission Transmission	MCMC, SC-Grid	—	Lothringer & Barman (2020) Lothringer et al. (2021)
METIS	Transmission	MCMC	—	Lacy & Burrows (2020)
Carrión-González et al.	Reflection	MCMC	—	Carrión-González et al. (2020)
ARCiS	Transmission Emission	NS	—	Min et al. (2020) Chubb & Min (2022)
PICASO	Reflection Emission Transmission	NS, SC-Grid	Link	Mukherjee et al. (2021) Miles et al. (2022) Batalha et al. (2023)
Cerberus	Transmission	MCMC	—	Swain et al. (2021)
Aurora	Transmission	NS	—	Welbanks & Madhusudhan (2021)
BART	Transmission Emission	MCMC	Link	Harrington et al. (2022)
ExoJAX	Emission	MCMC	Link	Kawahara et al. (2022)
ThERESA	Eclipse Mapping	MCMC	Link	Challener & Rauscher (2022)
p-winds	Transmission	MCMC	Link	Dos Santos et al. (2022)
HyDRo	Emission	NS	—	Piette et al. (2022)
smarter	Transmission	NS	—	Lustig-Yaeger et al. (2022)
tierra	Transmission	MCMC	Link	Niraula et al. (2022)
rfast	Reflection Emission Transmission	MCMC	Link	Robinson & Salvador (2023)
Machine Learning				
HELA	Transmission	RF	Link	Márquez-Neila et al. (2018)
ExoGAN	Transmission	NN	Link	Zingales & Waldmann (2018)
INARA	Reflection Emission	NN	Link	Soboczenski et al. (2018)
plan-net	Transmission	NN	Link	Cobb et al. (2019)
Fisher et al.	Transmission	RF	—	Fisher et al. (2020)
Johnsen & Marley	Reflection	MLP	Link	Johnsen et al. (2020)
Nixon & Madhusudhan	Transmission	RF	—	Nixon & Madhusudhan (2020)
MARGE+HOMER	Emission	NN+MCMC	Link	Himes et al. (2022)
exoCNN	Transmission	NN	Link	Ardevol Martinez et al. (2022)
VI-retrieval	Transmission	NN+VI	—	Yip et al. (2022)
Vasist et al.	Emission	NN+VI	—	Vasist et al. (2023)

Table 1 *continued*

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Code / Authors	Spectrum Type	Parameter Exploration	Code Link	References
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NOTE—Retrieval codes are ordered according to their first published exoplanet retrieval application (on either real or simulated spectroscopic data) for each category of exoplanet spectra. For years when multiple codes were published, the order is determined by the date of first arXiv submission. ‘Emission’ refers to secondary eclipse emission spectra, phase-resolved emission spectra, or direct thermal emission from a self-luminous object (i.e. directly imaged exoplanets or brown dwarfs). Parameter exploration acronyms are as follows: Optimal Estimation (OE); Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC); Nested Sampling (NS); Self-Consistent Grid (SC-Grid); Random Forest (RF); Neural Network (NN); Multilayer Perceptron (MLP); and Variational Inference (VI). Publicly available retrieval codes, at the time of this publication, have links to the code repository.

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